

MERCURY ADSORPTION USING GUIDE-PATTERNED POROUS GOLD

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1 Introduction

Metallic porous materials are increasingly being looked at for use substrate for nano/bio sensor and catalysis, due to their high surface-to-volume ratio [1]. Among metallic porous materials, porous gold has specially performance to biocompatibility, conductivity and stability. And porous gold is believed to be a good candidate as a substrate for batteries, sensors, and catalysts, while gold-conjugated protein has been proposed for use in sensing electrode systems.

Porous metal is generally fabricated by selective dealloying or templating method. In the dealloying method, white-gold (Au-Ag) alloy is employed, and Ag elements were selectively removed by chemical etching. In the templating method, multi-processing steps are involved. The metal is deposited into the artificial templates with different sizes, followed by removal of the templates to form the porous structure with an adjustable pore size. In our previous report, porous gold electrode was shown to be very effective and promising for the development of high performance electrochemical and biological sensors. PAu/ITO electrode functionalized with thiol groups (HDT, 1,6-hexanedithiol) have been successfully applied to the detection of mercury ion at very low concentration and display high linearity from 7 to 150 ppb. In addition, Pt nanoparticle-deposited PAu-pellet electrode also exhibits an extremely low working potential, a detection limit of 50 μM of H_2O_2 , and a fast response time within 10-20 sec.

Herein, we prepared line pattern of porous gold material to prepare metal ion detector. To fabricate micro-devices, PDMS-pattern was used. Micro-imprinting method is one of the most representative methods in soft lithography. Mercury ion detection was tested with both porous gold pattern and gold nanoparticle pattern which was prepared by Frens method.

2 Experiment

2.1 Preparation of PDMS pattern

We used PDMS (Sewang Hitech Silicone) of Sylgard-184A and DC-184B. Master pattern was prepared with silicon wafer by photo-lithography. First, Sylgard-184A and DC-184B mixed with appropriate ratio, and waited for an hour at room temperature to remove air bubble in PDMS pattern. Throw on master pattern on heating oven at 80°C for 5-6 hrs. After all step, PDMS is solidified and duplicated master pattern.

Fig.1. Schema of porous gold pattern.

2.2 Preparation of porous gold pattern

The aluminum precursor (aluminum sec-butoxide) and surfactants (stearic acid and magnesium stearate) were separately dissolved in sec-butyl alcohol. A gold precursor (HAuCl_4) was added to a solution of dissolving surfactant. The two solutions mixed, followed by slow addition of water at the rate of 1 ml/min. NaBH_4 was used as reducing agent. The resulting mixture showed a dark brown color. Stirring was continued for 24 hrs. After pass by 24 hrs, mixture spread on ITO glass. PDMS pattern put on ITO glass and inflict pressure. The material was dried at 80°C and calcined at 550°C in air, followed by etching with acid etchants (mixture of 11.8 M H_3PO_4 and 0.6 M HNO_3). Finally, pure porous gold with a brown color was obtained. The molar ratio of this react-ion mixture was 1 $\text{Al}(\text{sec-BuO})_3$: 0.09 HAuCl_4 : 0.2 surfactant: 10 sec-BuOH: 7 H_2O .

2.3 Characterization with porous gold pattern

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with energy di-spersive spectroscopy (EDS) were performed using a JSM-6700F (Jeol). Current-time response was recorded with potentiostat (WESI 500, WonA Tech). Pt substrate and Ag/AgCl are used as counter and re-reference electrodes, respectively.

Fig.2. Description of potentiostat

3 Results and Discussion

Porous gold showed a coral-like structure, which is helpful to transport target materials into the inner space. On the other hand, electrolytic-deposited gold on ITO glass showed rough surface morphology with no pore structure. PAu showed a window pore size of 200-400 nm and a framework thickness of 100-300 nm. PAu has many window pores formed due to the overlapping of the branched gold networks, which is the foundation of the interconnected pore system. Formation of submicron-sized window pores was induced by the removal of the alumina framework during the etching step. In XRD analysis, etched PAu showed the same characteristics peaks at (111), (200), and (220) as compared to bulk gold. Primary particle size of etched PAu was easily calculated to be ca. 40 nm by the Scherrer equation. Therefore, the framework of PAu was prepared by aggregation of primary gold particles during successive calcination, etching, and sintering processes.

Fig.3. AFM image of Silicon wafer (a) and SEM images of PDMS pattern (b and c).

As shown in Fig. 3, silicon wafer made by photolithography and that transferred PDMS pattern. We have prepared PDMS is based on replica molding [2]. Advantage of replica molding is completely identical copied original pattern. Second the samples need not to undergo high temperature; that is, even non-heat-resistant molecules will not be destroyed throughout the process [3]. And the advantages of incorporating specifically tailored micro-nanostructures into other structures to obtain multilevel masters with ordered patterns in a single step [4].

Lining pattern was same about patterned or un-patterned cause final results were had same shape. More it used only lining pattern. Porous gold pattern be able to more pore. Lining pattern had lot of areas compared other pattern for this reason, in this study we used to only lining pattern.

Fig.4. SEM images of before sintering (a and b), etched for 6 h (c and d) and 1 day (e and f). Depending on the etched time, alumina template was removed except porous gold pattern.

Fig. 4 is SEM images of porous gold patterning on glass. To make a porous gold, we mixed gold precursor (HAuCl_4) and surfactant (stearic acid or magnesium stearate). And then, gel state of porous gold is transferred on the glass using replica molding method before formation of a pore.

To remove a alumina template, phosphoric acid are used, and remaining organic materials and alumina template were removed over the sintering (550°C) step. Depending on the etching time (6 ~ 24 h), residues of alumina template was remained on the surface of porous gold pattern (Fig. 4c and 4d)[5].

Disadvantage of this method is difficult to cover on the surface of pattern with porous gold perfectly. As time goes by etching, residual gold was removed, gold was finally put on desired lining pattern. Because more pressing power is took to line section, and line pattern is more strong than the other surface.

Herein, to determine the maximum current per unit area, excess concentration of mercury ion was successively added in the form of 5 μM Hg^{2+} solution to the working vessel. Amperometric responses of the as-made electrode showed a typical stair-form of current change. The current response was linearly dependant on the mercury concentration in the range from 0 to 30 μM , but it approached maximum current density (80 μA per 2 cm^2 of electrode). Namely, for the full concentration range of mercury ion, the curve of the amperometric response was similar to that of Langmuir adsorption, which was due to adsorption of mercury ion on the thiol groups with oxo-bridge bonding (S-O-Hg-O-S). Since ionic conductivity correlated with $C^{1/2}$ by the Kohlraush equation and current density was linearly dependent on ionic conductivity, the Langmurian current response was obtained in the full range of concentrations.

Reference

- [1] Y. Li, W. -Z. Jia, Y. -Y. Song, X. -H “Hydrogen bubble dynamic template synthesis of porous gold nonenzymatic electrochemical detection of glucose”, *Electrochem. Commum*, Vol 9, pp 981, 2007
- [2] H. Kim, Y. Kim “Preparation of nanoporous gold using PS bead, Ludox and nanoporous alumina” as physical templates”, *Current Applied Physics*, Vol 9, pp 588-590, 2009
- [3] H. Kim, Y. Kim, J. Joo, J. Ko, J. Yi “Preparation of coral-like porous gold for metal ion detection”, *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, Vol 122, pp 283-287, 2009
- [4] D. B. Weibei, W. R. DiLuzio, G. M. Whitesides “Microfabrication meets microbiology”. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, Vol. 55, pp 209-218, 2007
- [5] A. Perl, D. N. Reinhoudt, J. Huskens, Microcontact printing: limitations and achievements, *Advanced Materials*, Vol. 21, 2257-2268, 2009